

Mobile Technologies applied to protect victims of a crime within the EU Area of Justice: RightsApp for e-Justice

D5.5 Four or more training sessions

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1	Report on tutorial videos and training sessions	31/08/2020	Jorge Gonzalez-Conejero (IDT-UAB)
2	Proof reading	03/09/2020	Mario Macias (IDT-UAB) and Andrea Guillén (IDT-UAB)

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document provides details regarding tutorials designed and implemented by the RightsApp research team. The support materials and the implementation features of the training session are also addressed in this document.

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1 TRAINING SESSIONS

The COVID-19 situation has reshaped all face-to-face activities in Europe for the past months. Consequently, and in order to adapt to the new circumstances, the RightsApp dissemination activities have also suffered deep changes with the aim of reaching the proposed objectives and milestones.

Given this scenario, the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB) and, specifically, the Faculty of Law hosted four online training sessions. The second semester of 2020 all lecture activities were moved to online channels. Therefore, the training sessions were held via Microsoft Teams¹ software that is available for all the UAB students and staff.

As support materials, the RightsApp research team created two tutorial videos. The first one explains how to use the Android version of the RightsApp application. The second video is focused on the iOS version of the RightsApp mobile application.

To sum up, four training sessions were held via Microsoft Teams between the 22nd and 26th of June 2020, with the following details:

Training session	Responsible	Attendants (approx.)
#1	Dr. Esther Zapater and Dr. Jorge Gonzalez-Conejero	15
#2	Dr. Esther Zapater and Dr. Jorge Gonzalez-Conejero	20
#3	Dr. Maria José Rodríguez Puerta and Dr. Jorge Gonzalez-Conejero	17
#4	Dr. Maria José Rodríguez Puerta and Dr. Jorge Gonzalez-Conejero	12
Total:		64

Table 1: Training sessions number, responsible and attendants.

Afterwards, the project coordinator, Dr. Jorge Gonzalez-Conejero, added the audio recording with the explanation of the video in order to disseminate the tutorials to the general public. Both videos were uploaded to YouTube and are publicly available at: <http://rightsapp-project.uab.cat/index.php/rightsapp-training-videos/>

Additionally, the Online Infoday presentation included in deliverable D5.7 RightsApp – “Public Events” was also useful to make all the RightsApp project information (motivations, background, needs, objectives, among others) available to the training session attendants.

¹ Microsoft Teams: <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/microsoft-365/microsoft-teams/group-chat-software>

2 VIDEOS

The designed and implemented tutorial videos cover different sections of the RightsApp mobile application (see RightsApp Deliverable D3.2: RightsApp Android Application² and/or D3.3: RightsApp iOS Application³)

- Main Screen
- Emergency call to 112
- Tailored information regarding crime victim rights
- Crime victim support centres, entities and, consulates and embassies
- Language selection
- “How to use the app” screen
- “About us” screen
- “Terms and Conditions” screen

Figure 1 depicts some screenshots from the tutorial videos. As mentioned before, the tutorial videos have been uploaded to YouTube with an audio explanation from the coordinator of the project in order to maximise their dissemination (for Android and iOS versions independently). Links to these videos can also be found in the RightsApp home page:

- YouTube link for the Android version: <https://youtu.be/1W0iV74a1A0>
- YouTube link for the iOS version: <https://youtu.be/8yl3Ur6dX4A>
- Link to the RightsApp home page: <http://rightsapp-project.uab.cat/index.php/rightsapp-training-videos/>

² RightsApp Deliverable D3.2: RightsApp Android Application. Available at: <https://zenodo.org/record/3263897#.X1FLR2czZQI>

³ RightsApp Deliverable D3.3: RightsApp iOS Application. Available at: <https://zenodo.org/record/3263909#.X1FLkGczZQI>

Figure 1: Screenshots from the RightsApp Training Videos for the Android version